

Carbon-13 NMR Spectra of Some Chromeno-Imidazole Derivatives

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In an earlier communication¹ the reactions of chromon-3-carboxylaldehyde (I) and 6-methyl chromon-3-carboxylaldehyde (II) with benzil and NH₄Ac in glacial HOAc were reported. The former afforded a product which was assigned 3(4',

the more convincing Carbon-13 NMR* data for the aforesaid reaction products of I and II as well as those of VII and VIII, supporting the formations of imidazoles III, VI, IX and X respectively. J_{C-H} for I, III, VI, IX and X are also reported. IX and X were obtained from VII and VIII respectively in a manner reported previously¹ for the preparations of III and VI.

A comparison of the Carbon-13 NMR signals and J_{C-H} (Table 1) for the different carbons of III with those of I strongly suggested the presence of 3-substituted chromone moiety in III. In addition to the signals for the carbons of the phenyl rings, the spectrum of III also displayed two weak singlets in the region 130-140 ppm in agreement with the presence of a fully substituted imidazole ring. Compounds VI, IX and X exhibited signals accountable for the appropriate substitution at C-6.

I	R ₁ = R ₂ = H
II	R ₁ = CH ₃ , R ₂ = H
VII	R ₁ = Cl, R ₂ = H
VIII	R ₁ = Br, R ₂ = H
XI	R ₁ = H, R ₂ = NH ₂

III	R = H
VI	R = CH ₃
IX	R = Cl
X	R = Br

5'-diphenylimidazole-2'-yl)-4(H)-oxo-1-benzopyran structure (III) in preference to 1H-2,3-diphenyl-5-hydroxy-6-(2'-hydroxy benzoyl)-1,4-diazepine (IV) or its tautomer V mainly on the basis of ¹H-NMR spectral data. The product from II was similarly assigned the structure VI. We report here

* Carbon-13 NMR spectra were run in CDCl₃. (δ_{TMS} = δ_{CDCl₃} + 76.9 ppm) on a Varian CFT-20 NMR spectrometer operating at 20.1 MHz in the FT mode and chemical shifts are in δ(ppm). In each case a proton noise decoupled and single frequency off-resonance decoupled spectra were run to establish the carbon shifts and the degree of protonation. Coupled spectra afforded the J_{C-H} values (Hz).

The C-4 carbonyls in all the compounds appeared in the region of 175 ppm. The chemical shifts of C-2 and C-3 carbons of the compounds III, VI, IX and X occurred in the region of 155 and 114 ppm respectively, whereas downfield shifts were observed for C-2 and C-3 in I and XI due to the presence of -CHO group at C-3. C-8 carbons in all the compounds resonated at the same regions irrespective of the *meta* substituents in the phenyl ring. C-4a carbons in the compounds III, VI, IX and X appeared in the region of 124 ppm whereas it absorbed at about 120 ppm for the compounds I and XI. C-5 and C-7 resonated uniformly in all the compounds except for the compounds VI and X where downfield shifts of about 1.5 ppm and about 3 ppm respectively were observed due to *ortho* effect². The chemical shifts of C-6 in all the compounds were in conformity with their structures: compounds I, III and XI absorbed in the same region but downfield shift of ~10 ppm and ~6 ppm and an upfield shift of ~5.5 ppm were observed for the compounds VI, IX and X respectively for the substituent effects of CH₃, Cl and Br groups at C-6. Chemical shifts of C-8a in all the compounds appeared nearly at the same position. The chemical shifts for C-2', C-4' and C-5' and those of phenyl ring carbons were uniform and in conformity with their structures.

The one bond coupling constants (J_{C-H}) of the oxygenated carbon C-2 in III, VI, IX and X was about 200 Hz which was closely comparable to the J_{C-H} for C-2 in I, indicating that C-2 was not fully substituted. J_{C-H} for aromatic and methyl carbons were in the normal range.

TABLE I—CARBON-13 CHEMICAL SHIFTS AND COUPLING CONSTANTS (J_{C-H}) OF I, III, VI, IX, X AND XI

	I	III	VI	IX	X	XI*
C-2	160.4 (198.1)	154.6 (200.1)	155.0 (199.6)	154.6 (201.0)	154.6 (201.1)	165.6
C-3	125.0	113.7	113.0	114.1	114.2	122.3
C-4	175.6	175.8	175.8	174.8	174.6	175.3
C-4a	120.1	123.5	123.1	124.5	124.8	120.0
C-5	126.3 (164.0)	125.5 (166.5)	124.8 (164.0)	125.0 (161.6)	128.4 (161.1)	125.4
C-6	125.8 (160.5)	125.4 (166.7)	135.7	131.6	119.1	125.3
C-7	134.6 (164.0)	133.7 (164.2)	135.2 (164.0)	134.0 (169.0)	136.8 (168.2)	134.2
C-8	118.4 (167.4)	118.1 (166.1)	117.9 (165.1)	119.9 (168.1)	120.1 (168.3)	116.9
C-8a	155.9	155.7	154.0	154.0	154.5	
C-2'		139.5	139.7	139.1	139.1	
C-4', 5'		132.6	131.4	131.6	132.0	
C-1'', 1'''		127.5	127.5	127.5	127.5	
C-2'', 2''', 6'', 6'''		127.5 (162.2)	127.5 (162.0)	127.5 (159.3)	127.5 (159.7)	
C-3'', 3''', 5'', 5'''		128.3 (160.2)	128.3 (160.4)	128.4 (160.5)	128.4 (161.1)	
C-4'', 4'''		127.1 (160.7)	127.3 (159.4)	127.2 (160.5)	127.2 (160.7)	
CHO	188.2 (186.5)					188.1
CH ₃			20.7 (125.2)			

* In d₆-DMSO; C-8a signal merged with noise.

References

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Search for Potent Anthelmintics-Part XIV. Benzoxazolylthio/Oxyethylureas and Thioureas

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A number of N¹-(2-benzoxazolylthio/oxyethyl)-N³-alkyl/arylureas and thioureas were synthesised as possible anthelmintics.

Several thioureas^{1,2} including benzimidazolyl thioureas³ have very recently been found as effective anthelmintics. A few ureas^{4,5} have also been known to reduce hook worms in dogs and possess nematocidal effect against *Panegrellus redivivus*. Moreover, some benzoxazole derivatives^{6,7} exhibited anthelmintic properties in mice and chickens. In view of these findings, it was considered desirable to synthesise the title ureas and thioureas with a view to determining their anthelmintic efficacy.

Benzoxazol-2-thione/one^{8,9} was refluxed with β -chloroethanolamine hydrochloride¹⁰ in the presence of acetone and anhydrous K₂CO₃ to afford 2-(2-aminoethylthio/oxy) benzoxazole. The latter was treated with various alkyl/aryl isocyanates or isothiocyanates to furnish the desired ureas and thioureas.

The results of anthelmintic screening of these compounds will be communicated later on.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr pellets.

I. 2-(2-Aminoethylthio)benzoxazole and 2-(2-aminoethoxy) benzoxazole :

A mixture of benzoxazol-2-thione or benzoxazol-2-one (.01 mole), β -chloroethanolamine hydrochloride (.01 mole), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (.02 mole) and acetone (100 ml) was refluxed for 16 to 20 hr on a steam bath. It was then cooled and filtered. Acetone was distilled off from the filtrate and the crude product obtained was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether.